

PRINCIPALS' CONFLICT MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, one research objective, one research question, and one null hypothesis were formulated. A correlational research design was adopted. The study population comprised 762 principals and 7,607 teachers across 254 public secondary schools. A sample of 381 principals (50% of the population) and 1,481 teachers (30% of the teaching population), totalling 1,862 respondents, was selected using a multistage sampling technique that combined purposive and stratified approaches. Two researcher-developed instruments—the Principals' Conflict Management Techniques Questionnaire (PCTQ) and the Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)—were used for data collection. Instrument validity was established through expert face validation, while reliability, tested with Cronbach's alpha, yielded coefficients of 0.81 and 0.90 for the independent and dependent variables, respectively. Regression coefficients were used to answer the research question, and simple linear regression analysis was employed to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed a significant relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance. It was recommended that principals adopt routine conflict resolution strategies to foster a conducive teaching and learning environment, thereby enhancing teachers' job performance.

Introduction

Education is widely recognised as a cornerstone of national development, as it equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for active participation in society. In Nigeria, education is viewed as a pathway to improved living conditions and socio-economic progress, and it has been formally adopted as an instrument for achieving national development (FRN, 2013). Despite this emphasis, persistent societal challenges, including insecurity, moral decline, drug abuse, and political and religious crises, have been linked to deficiencies in the quality of education. Public secondary schools, in particular, often fail to adequately prepare school leavers with the competencies needed to overcome poverty, secure employment, and contribute to national growth.

The introduction of free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State has led to a sharp rise in student enrolment without corresponding increases in teacher recruitment or infrastructure provision. Overcrowded classrooms, dilapidated facilities, and inadequate accommodation have created severe managerial and pedagogical challenges. In some schools, staff rooms are converted into classrooms, making lesson preparation difficult. Principals face reduced capacity for effective supervision, while teachers' morale declines under poor working conditions and bureaucratic barriers to communication. These issues have negatively affected teachers' job performance and student learning outcomes (Owan & Agunwa, 2021).

The success of any school system depends largely on the competence and commitment of principals and teachers. Principals, as chief administrators, influence teachers' job performance through their management techniques, which include decision-making, supervision, capacity building, and conflict resolution (Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2020; Hallinger, 2020). Effective management practices are known to enhance staff morale, improve productivity, and create environments conducive to teaching and learning (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

Teachers' performance, on the other hand, is reflected in the successful execution of instructional tasks such as lesson preparation and delivery, classroom management, student assessment, and the introduction of innovative teaching strategies. However, overcrowded classrooms, sometimes exceeding the 1:40 teacher-student ratio recommended by the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), often undermine teachers' effectiveness (Mulryan-Kyne, 2020). Research indicates that teachers' effectiveness is influenced not only by subject knowledge and pedagogy but also by their ability to maintain order, adapt to challenges, and operate in supportive work environments (Kraft & Falken, 2021).

As leaders of school systems, principals are expected to demonstrate competence in areas such as supervision, communication, mentoring, decision-making, capacity building, and conflict management. Among these, conflict management is particularly critical, as unresolved conflicts can disrupt academic activities, reduce teamwork, and lower teacher morale (Bush & Glover, 2016; Rahim, 2017). Conflict in schools often arises when the interests of individuals or groups clash, impeding collective goals. When principals neglect conflict management, teachers may become resentful, cooperation may break down, and job performance may decline. Conversely, effective conflict management fosters mutual trust, collaboration, and an enabling school climate that supports teaching and learning.

Statement of the Problem

Effective school administration requires principals to demonstrate strong managerial competence, particularly in conflict management, while teachers are expected to remain committed to instructional delivery and professional responsibilities. In

Akwa Ibom State, however, the rapid expansion of free and compulsory education has resulted in overcrowded classrooms, overstretched infrastructure, and inadequate teacher recruitment. These systemic challenges have placed significant strain on both teachers' job performance and principals' administrative capacity.

Teachers in many public secondary schools are often assigned subjects outside their areas of specialisation due to manpower shortages, while some are employed on an ad hoc basis without the requisite professional qualifications. The lack of mentorship and limited opportunities for professional development further reduce instructional effectiveness. At the same time, teachers are frequently excluded from decision-making processes, which contributes to low morale and disengagement.

One of the most critical yet underexplored challenges is the escalation of conflicts within schools. Conflicts arise from poor communication, overcrowding, resource scarcity, and strained relationships among teachers, students, and administrators. Left unmanaged, these conflicts disrupt academic calendars, reduce cooperation among staff, and contribute to absenteeism, insubordination, and negligence of duty among teachers. Ultimately, the absence of effective conflict management undermines teachers' job performance, leading to declining student outcomes and reduced educational quality.

While previous studies have examined teacher performance and school management in Nigeria, limited research has specifically focused on the role of principals' conflict management techniques in shaping teachers' effectiveness. This gap is significant, as evidence from both local and international contexts suggests that effective conflict management is central to fostering collaboration, maintaining staff morale, and sustaining school productivity (Bush & Glover, 2016; Rahim, 2017; Leithwood et al., 2020). Addressing this gap is essential to improving the performance of teachers and ensuring that public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State can deliver on their mandate of preparing students for meaningful contributions to society.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

To guide the study, this null hypothesis was formulated:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design, which was considered appropriate because it enabled the examination of the relationship between principals' conflict management techniques (independent variable) and teachers' job performance (dependent variable) without manipulating either variable. In this context, correlational design is both practical and ethical, as it allows for the description of naturally occurring relationships (McCombes, 2009).

The study population comprised all principals, vice principals (academic, administration, and special duties), totaling 762, and 7,607 teachers across the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State during the 2019/2020 academic session (SEB, 2019). From this population, a multistage sampling procedure was employed, incorporating purposive, stratified, and cluster sampling. Vice principals were included alongside principals due to their administrative responsibilities. Public secondary schools were stratified by senatorial district, and further clustered by local government area, number of schools, principals, and teachers. This distribution comprised 9, 12, and 10 local government areas; 89, 72, and 93 schools; 89, 72, and 93 principals; and 3,453, 1,294, and 2,860 teachers, respectively.

From this distribution, 160 schools (50%), 381 principals (50%), and 1,481 teachers (30%) were selected through simple random sampling, yielding a total sample size of 1,862 respondents. Within each school, a minimum of 12 teachers were sampled to ensure adequate representation. Each principal rated at least four teachers, and each teacher rated one principal, establishing reciprocal rating ratios of 1:4 and 4:1. This strategy was considered sufficient to ensure representativeness and reliability of responses (see Appendix 1 for the sampling frame).

Two researcher-developed instruments were employed for data collection: the *Principals' Conflict Management Techniques Questionnaire (PCTQ)* and the *Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)*. The PCTQ measured principals' conflict management techniques across seven sub-variables, each represented by eight items, giving a total of 56 items. It was rated by teachers. The TJPQ assessed teachers' job performance across five domains: classroom management, lesson delivery, student evaluation, innovation in teaching, and subject content knowledge. It consisted of 20 items and was rated by principals. Both instruments were subjected to expert face validation to ensure content appropriateness. Reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded coefficients of 0.81 for the PCTQ and 0.90 for the TJPQ, indicating satisfactory internal consistency.

Prior to data collection, ethical clearance was obtained from the relevant institutional review board. Permission was also secured from the State Secondary Education Board and school authorities. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without penalty.

Results

The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Principals' Conflict Management Techniques and Teachers' Job Performance

<i>Source</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>Regression</i>	178,604.40	1	178,604.40	514.97	.000	Significant
<i>Residual</i>	492,834.52	1421	346.82			
<i>Total</i>	671,438.92	1422				

Note. $N = 1,423$. $p < .05$. Source: Field data (2021).

The regression analysis revealed a calculated F value of 514.97 and a p-value of .000, which is less than the significance threshold of .05 at 1,422 degrees of freedom. Accordingly, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result therefore indicates that there is a significant relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent of the relationship between principals' conflict management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship, suggesting that principals who adopt effective conflict management strategies foster harmonious working environments that enhance teachers' commitment and instructional effectiveness.

This outcome aligns with international evidence that effective conflict management promotes collaboration, reduces stress, and improves organisational outcomes (Rahim, 2017; Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2020). When principals resolve conflicts impartially and in a timely manner, they contribute to a school climate that supports teacher motivation and productivity (Hallinger, 2020; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Conversely, poorly managed conflicts can lead to dissatisfaction, absenteeism, and disengagement, ultimately undermining student outcomes (Bush & Glover, 2016; Kraft & Falken, 2021).

Previous Nigerian studies also provide supporting evidence. For example, Ukpabio (2005) reported that principals' conflict management approaches significantly influenced teachers' job performance in Cross River State, while Etim (2005) found that organisational conflict was significantly associated with teacher dissatisfaction and reduced efficiency. The present findings build on these earlier works by providing more robust evidence, based on a large sample of 1,862 respondents, that effective conflict management is central to sustaining teacher performance in public secondary schools.

This study therefore contributes to both local and global scholarship by demonstrating that conflict management is not merely an administrative responsibility but a critical determinant of teachers' effectiveness and, by extension, school success.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that principals' conflict management techniques have a significant relationship with teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This confirms that the ability of school leaders to effectively manage disputes is central to sustaining teacher motivation, enhancing classroom practices, and improving overall school outcomes.

The study concludes that conflict management is not only an administrative responsibility but also a strategic tool for fostering collaboration, promoting teacher professionalism, and ensuring that educational objectives are achieved. Where principals adopt timely, impartial, and constructive approaches to resolving conflicts, teachers are more likely to perform effectively and contribute positively to students' academic achievement. Conversely, neglect or mismanagement of conflicts lowers teacher morale, reduces efficiency, and compromises the quality of education delivered in public secondary schools.

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Capacity building for principals: Principals should be trained in modern conflict management strategies through regular workshops, seminars, and professional development programmes. This will equip them with the skills needed to mediate disputes impartially, maintain harmonious school environments, and enhance teachers' performance.
- ii. Timely conflict resolution: School leaders should adopt proactive measures to address conflicts before they escalate into crises. Early intervention fosters trust, prevents disruption of academic activities, and sustains teacher morale.
- iii. Inclusive decision-making: Principals should encourage participatory leadership by involving teachers in decision-making processes. Inclusive governance promotes mutual respect, reduces resentment, and strengthens teamwork within schools.
- iv. Policy support: The State Secondary Education Board and the Ministry of Education should institutionalise conflict management as a core component of school leadership policies. Guidelines, monitoring mechanisms, and accountability systems should be put in place to ensure that principals handle conflicts effectively.

- v. Further research: Future studies should examine the specific conflict management strategies that are most effective in improving teachers' job performance, including comparative analyses across states or countries. Such research would enrich the literature on school leadership and provide evidence for policy and practice.

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